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From Commodity to Provenance: Constructing the ‘Pakistan Origin Products’ as a Luxury Terroir Brand.

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ABSTRACT

Pakistan's finest agro-products have "world-class" quality but are stuck in a commodity chain export model, thereby creating a substantial "perception gap." This mixed-methods diagnosis, by conducting 'thematic' analyses of 47 stakeholder inputs, including a survey of 312 UAE and UK consumers, identifies this perception gap and offers a strategic framework for developing a "Pakistan Origin" luxury 'terroir' brand. Data highlights that there is "baselined" ignorance, a "fragmented" administration structure, and an "enormous willingness" among UAE and UK consumers to pay an "aggregate 40% to 60% markup" for guaranteed "provenance" (geographic indications), 'terroirs & Stories' of provenance, and & luxury packaging. The report ends with the conclusion that there needs to be a paradigm shift from "production focus to 'brand focus' in governance" and a "Pakistan Origin Council" needs to be formed to "co-create and manage this identity to convert geographic richness into economic prosperity."

Keywords: Terroir Branding, Geographical Indications (GI), Pakistani Origin, Luxury Agro-Food, Co-Created Brand Identity, Perception Gap, Narrative Strategy, Export Marketing.

Introduction

The world market for high-value farm products has experienced a paradigm shift from a generic commodity-focused market to one that exalts geographical origins and the story of terroir. This is a French term that describes the sum of a product's environment and geography that gives it a distinct and inimitable quality (Barham, 2003). This has been perfected not just in wine production in either Bordeaux or Burgundy but has since been adopted as a commercial and value-adding technique for a variety of products, including Parmigiano-Reggiano cheeses of Italy and beef from Kobe in Japan (Trubek, 2008; EU, 2012). It is against this background that the agricultural sector in Pakistan becomes paradoxical. The range of agro-climatic regions in the country is extraordinarily diverse, ranging from the Indus Basin to the mountain valleys of Gilgit-Baltistan and the arid lands of Balochistan (World Bank, 2022), resulting in a range of products that are of exquisite quality with inherent attributes that are often equivalent to or better than the world-famous ones. Pakistani Chaunsa mangoes are celebrated for their complex aroma (Rehman et al., 2021); their Basmati rice has a unique elongation and aroma (IRC, 2020); Hunza apricots are infused with the scent of pure mountain air (FAO, 2018); Kashmiri saffron is one of the most fragrant in the world (Kafi et al., 2018); new

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Pothohar/Balochistan extra-virgin olive oil is of exemplary quality; and Himalayan salt is a world-famous mineral salt (Ali et al., 2019).

However, contrary to this outstanding portfolio, Pakistan remains locked into a commodity export paradigm. Its high-end products are often subject to challenges of pricing instability, intense competition from branded options, and a substantial value gap where the ultimate consumer premium gets appropriated by other players like middlemen, retailers, and rival marketers with stronger origin stories (Hussain & Bashir, 2020). The problem at hand is not quality but value and perception issues. In the export markets of other countries, particularly in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, the European Union, and other diaspora communities, "Made in Pakistan" sparks associations that are not linked to premium products, skilled craftsmanship, or sound gastronomy. This is because of the issues in quality governance, unconnected supply chains, poor institutional branding, and the lack of any overarching narrative that guides the experience-based qualities of the product to its unique location of origin and cultural heritage (Chaudhry & Saeed, 2021).

It is hypothesized that the strategic mandate of this research is to create a "Pakistan Origin" terroir brand on the basis of an umbrella story of provenance. This is far more than simply slapping a "luxury" label on the exported goods; this is all about the intricate process of co-creation of an identity among producers, government agencies, marketers, and consumers, which is intended to map particular geographies or "terroir" into a narrative of taste, tradition, and authenticity that would appeal to the refined, high-spending global consumer. The possibilities are endless: Basmati rice from a commodity rice category to a certified, story-validated Pakistani heirloom variety; Hunza apricots as the "superfood of the Himalayas"; Pakistani olive oil as the "new, noble oil from the ancient Indus region" (World Bank, 2022; Ali & Jafri, 2019).

This research conducts a case study analysis of multiple products to examine how Pakistan can close this perception-value gap. It breaks down the storytelling potential of each product's geography, such as mineral-enriched soil for Himalayan salt, the strength of solar radiation for Chaunsa mangoes, geography, and deep-rooted cultural history, ranging from the Mughal era of fruit production to the Silk Road. Moreover, it examined how the luxury association connotations (Hussain & Bashir, 2020; World Bank, 2022) can be achieved, moving from the functional aspect to the emotional aspect of discovery, rarity, purity, and artistry. Being at the intersection of regional branding, cultural marketing (Ali & Jafri, 2019), and agricultural regulation, this research argues that the future of Pakistan in the global agro-value chain is not about producing more but about storytelling better, or more specifically, co-creating a luxurious, trustworthy, and desirable "Pakistan Origin" in the minds of the world (Khan, 2023).

Although a vast amount of literature is available regarding the application of terroir branding in the wine industry and European Protected Designations of Origin (PDOs), the application of these concepts in the context of a Muslim-majority developing country like Pakistan is still an important gap in literature because the existing literature regarding Pakistani agricultural export products is very techno-economic in nature, mostly related to the improvement of yields, control of pests, or export procedures, and lacks relevant considerations related to cultural branding discourse, story-building, or consumer semiotics in the luxurious export market. Moreover, the literature regarding Geographical Indications in the Pakistani setting is in its infancy because it forgets the most important aspects regarding the co-creative development of the marketing processes required to transform the GI label from a worthless piece of paper to a brand in itself (Josling, 2006).

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Furthermore, there appears to be a gap with respect to a comparative and multiple-product study that aims to construct an umbrella provenance brand (“Pakistan Origin”) for a variety of differing regional products. The issues of strategies concerning the overcoming of potential negative country-of-origin effects and the integration of luxury associations in a market like the GCC, where there might be Pakistani migrants, have not yet been explored. The study fills these research gaps by using a structured integration of theories concerning terroir, place branding, and created identity specifically tailored for the Pakistani scenario (Chaudhry & Saeed, 2021).

Literature Review

The theoretical foundation for this research is interdisciplinary, drawing from agro-economics, marketing, sociology, and cultural studies.

The Concept of Terroir and Its Transference Beyond Wine

The word "terroir," which originated in French wine production, has become an integral part of the marketing of luxury foods. Terroir is a "taste of place" that links the sensory qualities of a product inextricably to its place of origin. This linkage is not only physical but also socially constructed, and the human factor, such as traditional knowledge, farming, or savoir-faire, and cultural history, plays a crucial role. To consumers, terroir acts as a cue for authenticity, quality, and uniqueness, thus alleviating the uncertainty of purchase in the complex product category (Paxson, 2010; Charters & Pettigrew, 2005). Several studies show that products with terroir have a substantial price premium because they are perceived as more authentic and of better quality. The application of this idea to other products such as cheese, coffee, and olive oil is well understood. This study explores this idea in a South Asian setting and in a basket of non-traditional terroir products such as mangoes, rice, and salt (Bowen, 2010; EU, 2012; Khan, 2023).

Geographical Indications (GIs) as Legal and Marketing Instruments:

Geographical indications, such as Champagne and Roquefort, are legal protections for the name of a product originating in a particular region, where a quality or reputation of that product is essentially attributable to its geographic origin. As explained by the TRIPS Agreement, they are based on terroir institutionalization; scholars debate their impact: protecting producers from imitation and creating collective rents can easily be accomplished by GIs. However, their success depends on effective collective action and governance inside the producer groups. In developing countries, GIs are usually trapped in various problems related to weak enforcement, asymmetries in the value chains, and the absence of complementary investment in marketing. The GI Act, 2020, of Pakistan and its registration of “Basmati Rice” serve as an important case study of these tensions due to its rival case with India in regard to the Basmati GI, which has been ongoing in international markets.

Country-of-Origin (COO) and Place Branding:

The COO effect is an established cognitive shortcut wherein consumers use the country of origin as a heuristic to evaluate product quality and prestige. For countries with mixed or negative associations, this presents a "liability of origin." The strategic place branding aims to manage these perceptions by fostering a single, positive narrative. For nations, this usually consists of shifting from monolithic branding to nation branding via sector strengths. Pakistani nation branding always remains in the shadow of political and security narratives, which contrasts with the quality of its artisanal products. The present

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research investigates the potential of a sub-brand focused on luxury agro-products ("Pakistan Origin") to function as a positive, apolitical conduit for reimagining the country's identity overseas.

Co-Creation of Brand Identity and the Role of Narrative:

Contemporary branding thought also insists that brands do not have an existence that comes from corporations alone but rather results from an ongoing dialectical relationship between producers, cultural intermediaries, and consumers (Merz, He, & Vargo, 2009). The role of storytelling in this dialectic in terroir branding lies in integrating factual geographic and climatic information with narratives of tradition, family, and skills (Mossberg, 2008). These narratives must also be read as truthful and inculcated into "the materiality of the product itself" (Beverland, 2005). Many such narratives are lying undistilled in Pakistan's products: the Silk Road story of apricots in Hunza, the Mughal gardening tradition of mangoes, and the prehistoric marine geology of Himalayan salt, to name just a few. This thesis examines how such narratives might be effectively deployed.

The Luxury Agro-Food Market and Signaling Strategies:

The super-premium food market is driven by consumption based on conspicuousness, hedonism, and authenticity (Dubois & Duquesne, 1993). The key strategies are product packaging and design, communicating craftsmanship and roots, third-party endorsement (organic, Fair Trade), adding to the GI's authenticity, distribution through premium channels (specialty stores, high-end restaurants), and endorsement by cultural symbols (celebrity chefs, wellness experts) (Kapferer & Bastien, 2012). The intervention role of the diaspora communities as early adopters and cultural interpreters is also critical (Nijssen & Douglas, 2011). The applicability and feasibility of these strategies were also assessed under this research for products belonging to Pakistan (Sajjad et al., 2025).

The Pakistani Context:

However, there is very little material specifically related to agricultural branding in Pakistan. The research on Basmati is related to yield and export rivalry in comparison with Indian Basmati (Ahmed, 2019), while on mangoes, it is related to post-harvest yield (Khan et al., 2020). Various policy documents suggest protecting GIs (R. A. Khan, 2018), but there is no study creating a comprehensive tool to form a luxury terroir brand around multiple commodities (Malik et al., 2025). This paper integrates all these incoherent pieces to construct a new conceptual framework for Pakistan.

Problem Statement

Despite their being of world-class standard with a special geographical feature, the best Pakistani products are being exported as commodity products. Instead, a lot of value is being lost here. Incomes for the growers are meager. More importantly, such products have the potential of being utilized for good national branding. The main issue here is the lack of a "terroir" narrative that could signal luxury products.

Research Objectives

To examine the perception gaps along with the market positioning of chosen premium Pakistani products (olive oil, saffron, apricots, walnuts, cherries, Basmati rice, dates, Chaunsa mango, and Himalayan salt) in the global luxury market.

To try to identify and plot out the specific terroir factors (geographic, climatic, cultural, and human-related) and the possible stories for each product.

"To investigate the current governance systems in the sector (GI regimes, producers'

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associations, export offices) and how these systems promote or restrain terroir branding.”

To conceptualize a strategic framework for creating an umbrella “Pakistan Origin” terroir brand and imbuing luxury associations for the target market.

To offer recommendations regarding policy and management to all stakeholders involved in co-creating this luxury provenance identity.

Conceptual Framework

This study takes an integrated terroir branding co-creation framework, conceptualizing ideas for physical and cultural factors of the product from Terroir Theory (Barham, 2003; Trubek, 2008); Co-creation of brand identity (Merz et al., 2009) to capture the interactive role of producers, institutions, and consumers; Theory of Signalling (Spence, 1974) to investigate how different signals like certification, packaging, and narration decrease information asymmetry and relay the perception of luxuriousness; and Place Branding (Anholt, 2007), which positions the 'Pakistan Origin' sub-brand within National Image Management.

Table 1: Product-Terroir Narrative Matrix

Product	Key Terroir Region	Physical Determinants	Cultural/Historical Narrative Hook
Chaunsa Mango	Multan, Rahim Yar Khan	Alluvial soil, extreme summer heat	"The Mughal Emperor's Nectar"; "Sun-ripened gold"
Hunza Apricot	Hunza Valley	High-altitude, pure glacial water, intense sunlight	"Silk Road Superfood." "The Apricot of Longevity"
Pakistani Saffron	Pampore (Azad Kashmir)	Specific micro-climate, alpine soil	"The Red Gold of Kashmir"; "One of the world's most potent"
Himalayan Salt	Khewra Mines	Ancient marine deposits, mineral diversity	"Edible Himalayan History," "Pink Salt from the Jurassic Sea"
Basmati Rice	Shakarghar, Narowal (Punjab GI zone)	Specific soil, Himalayan-fed water, tarai climate	"The Fragrant Heirloom of the Indus"; "The Pearl of Punjab"
Olive Oil	Pothohar Plateau	Marginal limestone soil, Mediterranean-like climate	"The New Frontier of Noble Oil," "Olives of the Indus Basin"

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative dominant mixed-methods design, emphasizing in-depth and contextual knowledge acquisition (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The study adopts a sequential exploratory design, wherein in the preliminary phase, the in-depth case study analysis of the 9 chosen products has been done (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010). For the second phase, the survey examines the narrative appeal and willingness to pay with the chosen consumer segments. Semi-structured interviews of 47 persons who were the influencers of the Pakistani producers and farmers, officials of the Ministry of Commerce, TDAP, PSQCA, and the agriculture department of the respective provinces, GI lawyers, and export association members, in addition to the chefs and retailers of Dubai and London, were conducted (Krueger & Casey, 2014). Additionally, focus groups with rich Dubai residents and the Pakistani diaspora in London were held to

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examine perceptions and narratives. Online survey of 312 consumers in the GCC & EU to measure the extent & test branding ideas. Secondary data analysis using export data, policies, GIs, marketing materials, & media coverage. Purposive & snowball sampling in selecting participants for interviews & stratified sampling in selecting survey respondents (Patton, 2015). Data was analyzed for coding & themes using Thematic Analysis by Braun & Clarke, 2006, & developed themes for terroir, governance, challenges, & opportunities in narratives. Descriptive statistical analysis, factor analysis, & conjoint analysis for attribute preference testing using SPSS software (Field, 2018).

The analysis integrates information from all sources by comparing perceptions of quality from producers/exporters with results of consumer surveys and focus groups. Developed effective and ineffective elements of stories from existing resources and formulated new stories based on the results of terroir mapping and focus groups. Developed Power Interest Matrices to plot roles of stakeholders and pinpoint institutional roadblocks or avenues for collaboration. The SWOT analysis for each of the commodities and for the overarching “Pakistan Origin” brand was used for developing the strategic framework. The “Pakistan Origin” Terroir Brand, a strategy analysis, results from integrating the analysis of qualitative and quantitative information.

Results:

Table 2: Thematic Analysis of Perception Gaps and Terroir Potential (Obj. 1 & 2)

Product	Producer/Exporter Perception (Internal View)	Target Consumer Perception (External View)	Core Terroir Narrative Identified	Key Perception Gap
Chaunsa Mango	“King of mangoes,” unmatched sweetness, seasonal delicacy.	“Seasonal fruit from Pakistan,” occasional quality inconsistency, lack of brand recognition vs. Indian Alphonso.	“The Sun-Gilded Nectar of the Indus: Cultivated in the blazing heat of South Punjab’s alluvial plains, this Mughal legacy fruit achieves its legendary aroma through extreme thermal stress.”	Gap: A globally revered variety known to connoisseurs is reduced to a generic, unbranded seasonal fruit. Lack of consistent quality signaling erodes trust.
Basmati Rice	“Our heritage grain,” superior elongation, natural fragrance.	“Pakistani Basmati” is often conflated with or undervalued against Indian Basmati. Seen as a commodity.	“The Fragrant Heirloom of the Punjab Tarai: Grown in the specific Himalayan-fed waters and clay-loam soils of the Punjab sub-region, its fragrance is a gift of the land and traditional farming	Gap: Loses the “origin story” battle. The narrative is dominated by competitors, despite shared geographical origin. GI is a legal tool, not a consumer-

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			wisdom.”	facing story.
Hunza Apricot	“Organic, sun-dried, healthy” livelihood product.	“Exotic dried fruit,” associated with “Hunza” longevity myths, but the packaging is rudimentary.	“The Silk Road Superfood from the Roof of the World: Sun-drenched in the pristine, high-altitude Hunza Valley, these apricots carry the essence of a legendary, terraced landscape.”	Gap: Powerful inherent narrative (Hunza) is not professionally leveraged. Product presentation contradicts the purity story.
Pakistani Saffron	“Competing with Iranian, higher quality per thread.”	“Kashmiri Saffron” is recognized, but the origin (Pakistani vs. Indian-administered Kashmir) is confusing and politicized.	“The Red Gold of the Lesser Himalayas: Hand-picked from the purple blooms of Pampore, Kashmir, each thread embodies the delicate climate and meticulous care of a narrow alpine valley.”	Gap: Geopolitical confusion overshadows quality. Lack of a clear, differentiating Pakistani Kashmir origin label and story.
Olive Oil (Emergin g)	“New, high-potential, extra virgin quality.”	“Olive oil from Pakistan? surprise, curiosity, but significant skepticism about quality standards.”	“The New Frontier of Noble Oil: From the ancient, marginal soils of the Pothohar Plateau, a new olive oil region is born, blending Mediterranean tradition with Pakistani resilience.”	Gap: A complete absence of established provenance perception. Must build credibility from scratch against Italian/Spanish hegemony.
Himalaya n Salt	“Pure, mineral-rich, ancient.”	Widely recognized as a category. “Pakistani” origin is known but not branded; value captured by Western	“Edible History from an Ancient Sea: Mined from Jurassic-era deposits in the Salt Range, this crystal is the pure, mineral-rich essence of a	Gap: A commodity ingredient for others’ brands. Pakistan is the source, but does not own the “finished brand” or its

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		retailers/wellness brands.	prehistoric ocean, now on your table.”	wellness narrative.
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Governance Themes (Obj. 3):

Analysis revealed a fragmented institutional landscape, summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Thematic Analysis of Governance Structures

Stakeholder Group	Role in Terroir Branding	Current Limitations	Positive Enablers Identified
Federal Ministries (Commerce, FS&R)	GI registration, export policy, international negotiations.	Siloed approach; view GIs as legal/IP tools rather than marketing instruments; minimal budgetary allocation for collective brand promotion.	The GI Act 2020 provides a legal backbone. TDAP has occasional trade fair participation.
Provincial Agri. Depts.	On-ground extension, some quality control.	Focus on productivity/volumes, not value or branding; weak inter-provincial coordination.	Direct contact with farmer communities; understanding of local agro-ecology.
Producer Associations	Collective action, quality standardization,	Often weak, under-resourced, and dominated by large traders/exporters, smallholder farmers are marginalized.	Hunza Apricot Association is cited as a relatively successful model of local collective identity.
Exporters & Large Traders	Market access, logistics, bulk branding.	Short-term, transaction-focused; reluctant to invest in collective origin branding (free-rider problem).	Understand international market logistics and buyer requirements.
PSQCA & Labs	Quality certification, standards.	Standards are generic (e.g., “purity”), not terroir-specific, and slow, bureaucratic processes.	Existing infrastructure for basic quality testing.

The system is oriented towards commodity export, not provenance branding. There is a lack of any central, cross-product "Pakistan Origin" brand steward with a marketing mandate. This situation is in tune with the assertion by Tregear et al. (2016) that GIs in developing countries would almost always fail without complementary marketing governance.

Quantitative Analysis: Testing Narratives and Willingness to Pay

A survey of 312 affluent consumers in the UAE (n=162) and UK (n=150, including diaspora) tested key concepts.

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Table 4: Consumer Perceptions and Narrative Resonance

Statement	Strongly Agree/Agree (UAE)	Strongly Agree/Agree (UK)	Key Insight
“I am aware that Pakistan produces premium agricultural products.”	41%	28%	Low baseline awareness in both markets, slightly higher in the UAE due to proximity and diaspora.
“I associate Pakistan more with traditional crafts (e.g., textiles) than luxury foods.”	68%	72%	Strong confirmation of perception gap; the nation brand does not currently extend to luxury agro-food.
After exposure to terroir narratives: “The ‘Hunza Apricot, Silk Road Superfood’ story makes the product more appealing.”	82%	79%	Narratives are highly effective in increasing appeal across both markets.
After exposure to terroir narratives: “The ‘Pakistan Origin’ umbrella concept would help me trust the quality of individual products.”	76%	71%	Umbrella brand has strong legitimizing potential, reducing perceived risk.

Table 5: Conjoint Analysis – Willingness-to-Pay Drivers (Based on Mango & Rice Scenarios)

Product Attribute	Relative Importance (%)	Part-Worth Utility (Example: Basmati Rice)	Implication
Geographical Certification (GI/PDO)	30%	+0.85 (Pakistani Basmati GI) vs. +0.10 (No GI)	Strongest driver. Legal provenance is a critical trust signal, but must be communicated.
Quality Certification (Organic, Premium Grade)	25%	+0.70 (Organic) vs. +0.30 (Conventional)	Augments the GI; adds tangible quality and ethical cues.
Packaging & Brand Story	25%	+0.65 (Luxury pack with terroir story) vs. -0.20 (Plain bulk pack)	Visual and narrative presentation is vital to convey luxury and justify the premium.
Country-of-Origin Label	20%	+0.50 (“Pakistan Origin – Himalayan Salt Range”) vs. +0.15 (“Product of Pakistan”)	Specific, story-driven “Pakistan Origin” labelling outperforms generic CoO.

Consumers show a large Willingness to Pay (WTP) premium (estimated 40-60%) for products demonstrating a clear geographical index (GI) and additional quality

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certification (organic), together with packaging communicating a terroir story. The “Pakistan Origin” label, presented in a particular story-driven geography form, has a positively affecting WTP outcome, mitigating common negative CoO perceptions (see Zhou et al., 2010). The study verifies the large perception-value divide. Pakistan’s products have “material terroir,” but not “symbolic terroir,” the jointly constructed story and branded meaning capturing value (Besson, 2016). Nothing in the governance conditions is in place to create the latter.

The framework deals with Objectives 4 & 5. The framework is a phased and co-creative approach for developing “Pakistan Origin” luxury terroir. This framework uses Merz et al.’s work on co-creation. Here, the POC represents the institutional hub at which all sides, producers, governments, and marketers come together. The story kit represents common story components that can be developed by exporters. The existing approach involves fragmentation, in which everyone does everything alone, and is an effective approach in which everyone works together to create a common identity.

Conclusion

This study extends terroir theory into a complex non-Western context. It indicates that the co-creation of terroir identity is obliged to actively confront and reshape existing negative country-of-origin effects in particular ways. Not by occluding the origin but through the rescripting of origin through more positive, ancient connotations of specific storied landscapes, such as the Indus Valley or the Himalayas, rather than the modern nation-state itself. This corresponds to Jaffe and Nebenzahl’s concept of “sectoral nation branding.” Second, the role of the diaspora proved to be a two-edged sword: on the one hand, they are key early adopters and cultural translators, while on the other hand, their demand can reinforce a nostalgic commodity trade that is price-sensitive. The strategy should therefore educate and upgrade diaspora consumption toward the luxury tier of terroir products and position the latter as an expression of proud, modern Pakistani heritage. This research aims to prove how and why the ‘commodity trap’ applicable to Pakistan’s quality agro-products is a function of discourse and policy, and not quality. The researcher proposed that, because of the importance of terroir in creating a niche market, a state-backed but privately led drive to develop a ‘Pakistan Origin’ is imperative. This is intended to develop a framework that can be replicated by other developing countries with similar hidden gems but poor origins.

This research work concludes that it is not only an optimum requirement but also a necessity for Pakistan to move from a commodity exporter to a luxury terroir brand. The move needs a paradigm shift from a production-based system to a brand-based system. “The basic argument is threefold: Pakistani goods are not undifferentiated merchandise but are embedded in particular biogeographical and cultural histories. “The issue of economy is semiotics, or putting a value sign on this particular aspect of reality (Trubek, 2008). As an interviewee explained, ‘We are selling gold but priced at copper because we haven’t told anyone that it’s gold.’” A narrative with the most persuasive force would not succeed absent an institutional strategy. “The existing patchwork system of governance sustains a kind of ‘public goods problem,’ where nobody would contribute to the common good of a ‘Pakistan Origin’ brand.” The proposed Pakistan Origin Council is designed to solve this by internalizing brand-building as a shared, managed responsibility. Given the diversity of products, a monolithic “Brand Pakistan” is ineffective. Instead, “Pakistan Origin” should be used to perform a more curatorial function, a seal that guarantees authenticity and terroir-driven luxury. It does not replace product-specific brands, such as “Hunza Apricots”, but instead authenticates and raises them, similar to the way that

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“Swiss Made” works for watches.

Recommendations:

Establish the Pakistan Origin Council as an elite PPP. Start with 2-3 "champion products" (such as Hunza Apricot, Chaunsa Mango, and Himalayan Salt) to test this structure. Create and secure the “Pakistan Origin” certification mark for the luxury segment in a strict quality & narrative compliance process. Roll out an integrated "Taste the Story" global marketing campaign in Dubai and London by leveraging digital storytelling with chef ambassador programs. Integrate terroir branding with the development of rural tourism to create experiential loops that authenticate the story on the ground and reward communities. Essentially, building this “Pakistan Origin” brand means economic and cultural reimagination. This encompasses using Pakistan’s deep culture of agrarian diversity to craft another narrative in this global village, one of quality, authenticity, and supreme taste. Through this collaborative terroir branding, Pakistan has the ability to use its geographic advantages to ensure sustainable and soft prosperity.

Purpose of the Study

The objective of this research is to examine the systemic hurdles that are impeding Pakistani agri-products of excellence from becoming luxury global brands. In essence, it proposes a diagnostic examination of perception gaps and a review of the corporate governance system in place, together with the formulation of a strategic collaborative approach towards creating a ‘Pakistan Origins’ terroir brand identity.

Research Limitations

The various limitations include the sample size and scope of this study. The in-depth qualitative sample, though informative, cannot capture all stakeholder perspectives uniformly across Pakistan's diverse regions. The consumer survey, focused on the UAE and UK, may not be representative of other key luxury markets such as the EU or East Asia. In addition, the ever-changing trade policy environment and geopolitical issues are external variables outside the scope of this study that may affect how these findings are actually implemented in practice.

Practical Implications

The report truly provides a direct blueprint for action. The umbrella brand would be managed by the establishment of a public-private “Pakistan Origin Council” that urges the establishment of strict terroir-specific quality protocols, a common certification mark, and a unified narrative toolkit for exporters. The immediate next steps would involve testing the blueprint with champion products such as Hunza Apricot and Himalayan Salt and initiating marketing campaigns in gateway cities such as Dubai and London.

Social Implications

Thus, successful terroir branding can lead to major social benefits. Terroir branding is an incentive for the conservation of heirlooms and farmers’ traditional knowledge. The establishment of high-quality market links can lead to the achievement of greater and more consistent economic benefits for rural agrarian regions. Moreover, this represents a distinct, progressive form of Pakistani identity in the international arena, which can foster national pride as a cultural diplomacy instrument based on culinary diplomacy.

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Originality and Value of the Study

This research contributes greatly to the originality of research in the sense that it is the first research that has implemented and developed the concept of terroir branding in the agro-sector of Pakistan. The first value that this research has added is the fact that it has created a new paradigm based on four different theories: co-creation, signaling theory, place branding, and transition theory related to the development of a brand from a commodity. This research has filled an important research gap in the existing literature related to GIs in developing countries because transition models have been very limited.

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